

MANUFACTURE AND OXIDATION BEHAVIOR OF C/SiC COMPOSITES MODIFIED WITH B-RICH SiBC COATING

X.Z. Zuo, L.T. Zhang, Y.S. Liu*, L.F. Cheng

(National Key Laboratory of Thermostructure Composites Materials, Northwest Polytechnical University, Xi'an 710072, China)

* Corresponding author (yongshengliu@nwpu.edu.cn)

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1 Introduction

Continue carbon fiber reinforced Silicon carbide ceramic matrix composites (C/SiC) have been developed and applied in high-temperature structural components due to their excellent physical and mechanical properties such as resistant to corrosion, high specific strength, and high specific modulus [1-3]. However, the residual porosity of approximate 10% exists in the composites as the shortage of CVI process, and micro-cracks are not avoided in matrix and coatings during annealing for the different coefficient of thermal expansion for carbon fiber and SiC matrix [4,5]. Oxygen diffuses from these defects (cracks and porosity) and reacts with carbonaceous material at temperature above 400 °C, which will degenerate mechanical properties of C/SiC. Therefore, C/SiC composites need to be modified with self-healing component, in order to improve oxidation resistance in high-temperature environment.

It is the aim of this investigation to modify two-dimensional C/SiC composite with self-healing B-rich SiBC coating by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and determine oxidation resistance at 700 °C, 1000 °C and 1200 °C.

2 Experimental Procedures

T300 carbon fiber from Japan Toray was employed, and 2D preforms were prepared from laminated carbon cloth, which was molded by graphite mold. Then, pyrolytic carbon (PyC) was deposited on the fiber. Thirdly, six layers of SiC were infiltrated by ICVI process. Fourthly, the as-received composite was machined and polished into samples with a dimension of 3mm×5mm×40mm. Finally, the SiC,

B-rich SiBC and SiC coating was deposited in sequence on the C/SiC composites.

Oxidation tests were conducted in a tube furnace in static air at 700 °C, 1000 °C and 1200 °C for 10h separately. Weight of the specimens were recorded via an electronic balance (sensitivity =0.01mg) after they were oxidized for 0, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 7 and 10h at the desired temperature respectively. After oxidation test, flexural strength of the samples were measured via a three bending test with a span of 30mm and a loading rate of 0.5mm/min at room temperature. Surface and cross-section morphologies of specimen were observed by SEM (JEOL6700F, Tokyo, Japan) before and after oxidation. And micro-chemical analysis was performed by the attached energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS, Oxford).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Characterization of CVD SiC/SiBC/SiC hybrid coatings

Known from the cross-section morphology of specimen modified with SiBC coating (Fig.1), the coatings are compact and the thickness of internal SiC, intermediate SiBC and exterior SiC coating are 30μm, 5μm and 70μm respectively. And meanwhile EDS result of intermediate SiBC coating is indicated that the coating is boron-rich. Phases in the SiBC coating are SiC and B₄C, which is conducted in other article [6].

3.2 Oxidation resistance of composites in static air environment

The weight change curves with the oxidation time and flexural strength retention after oxidation are shown in Fig.2. From Fig.2 (a), the weight loss of specimen increases linearly with oxidation time at 700 °C and 1200 °C. And meanwhile, it reaches

maximum value of 1.2% after oxidation for 10h at 700 °C during all the oxidation temperature. At 1000 °C, the weight of specimen decreases during first 0.5h, and then keeps constant. The change of residual strength is consistent with the change of weight. At 700 °C and 1200 °C, the weight loss are both higher than that at 1000 °C, meanwhile, the strength retention are both lower than that at 1000 °C. After oxidation for 10h at 1000 °C, the weight loss and the strength retention of specimen are 0.14% and 90.8% respectively.

Known from surface morphologies of specimen (Fig.3), there is no borosilicate glass oxidized from SiBC coating on the surface of specimen, and crack existing in coating is not healed after oxidation 10h at 700 °C (Fig.3a). Carbon fiber is not oxidized obviously, observed from SEM of cross-section morphology (Fig.4a). As temperature increasing to above 1000 °C, parts of cracks in the coating are healed by borosilicate glass oxidation 10h (Fig.3b and Fig.3c). Borosilicate glass can prevent efficiently oxygen penetrating, and carbon fiber is well protected and not oxidized after oxidation 10h. That is why the specimen has a good oxidation resistance at 1000 °C (Fig.4). When temperature increased to 1200 °C, the oxidation model is not-uniform [7]. Fiber bundle close to surface is badly oxidized from Fig.4c and Fig.4d; even through the crack is healed by borosilicate glass (Fig.3c). But for the inner area of specimen, carbon fiber is only oxidized. That is because volatilization of borosilicate glass accelerates as oxidation temperature increasing [8,9], which results in oxygen diffusion into composites much easily. And meanwhile, the oxidation process is controlled by the diffusion of oxygen at this temperature [10], the more amount of oxygen diffuses, the oxidation of carbon is more serious.

3.3 Oxidation model and mechanisms

To better understand the oxidation process of C/SiC composites modified with B-rich SiBC coating, the oxidation model is shown in Fig.5. The cracks have existed in coatings and matrix of C/SiC composites during fabrication process, which can provide routes for oxygen diffusion as shown in Fig.5a. When the specimen is oxidized at low temperature below 1000 °C, partial cracks only existing in SiBC coating are sealed by borosilicate glass; the others are still unrestricted and open for oxygen diffusion, which

leads to the properties of C/SiC composites degradation. With oxidation temperature increasing, oxidation reaction of SiBC coating accelerates and insults in much more borosilicate glass formation which can seal cracks in the coating. However, as temperature increasing to 1200 °C, viscosity of borosilicate glass decreases [11], and volatilization also accelerates, which badly affects the self-healing behavior of B-rich SiBC coating. The oxygen diffuses into composites from the borosilicate glass, and reacts with carbonaceous material, as shown in Fig. 5c.

During all the oxidation temperature, the follow reactions maybe occur:

Reactor (1), (4) and (6) will lead to weight loss, and others result in weight gain. At 700 °C, B₄C in the B-rich SiBC coating reacts with oxygen to form B₂O₃ (reaction (3)), which can seal partial crack. However, oxygen will diffuse easily from unsealed cracks, and react with carbonaceous material, as shown reaction (1), which leads to weight loss and mechanics performance of specimen degradation, meanwhile, the volatilization of B₂O₃ (reaction (4)) is also a weight loss process, that is why weight of specimen oxidized at 700 °C is loss and residual flexural strength decreases. As oxidation temperature increasing, the amount of borosilicate glass will increase, due to reaction (2), (3) and (5) accelerating, which can seal cracks existing in coatings effectively and protect the carbonaceous material from oxidizing. With temperature increasing to 1200 °C, on one hand, reaction (6) will accelerate and lead to volatilization of borosilicate glass. On the other hand, viscosity of glass also decreases. Therefore, oxygen diffusion become much easily and reacts with carbon fiber close to coating (Fig. 4c).

4 Conclusions

C/SiC composites modified with B-rich SiBC coating exhibit a good oxidation resistance at 1000

°C. Cracks existing in coating can be effectively seal-healed by borosilicate glass. Weight loss rate and flexural strength retention of specimen are 0.14% and 90.8% after oxidation 10h at 1000 °C respectively.

Fig.1 Morphology of C/SiC modified with SiBC coating and EDS result of SiBC coating

Fig.2 Oxidation behaviors of composites in static air environment

Fig.3 Surface morphologies of specimen oxidation at different temperature

Fig.4 Cross-section morphologies of specimen oxidation at different temperature

Fig.5 Oxidation model of specimen at different temperature
 (a) As-received (b) Oxidation at low temperature (below 1000 °C)
 (c) Oxidation at high temperature (above 1000 °C)

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